

Males. GLH males were taken from stock cultures at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) and IRRI and preserved in 70% ethanol. Visual comparison of the insects showed two distinct color morphs: one with black-spotted corium on tegmen and the other with uniformly green tegmen. The spotted morph occurred more frequently in both populations. Most of the nonspotted insects had relatively higher morphometric values for genital and abdominal characters than the spotted GLH.

Morphological dimensions and setal counts (Table 1) of genital components (Fig. 1) of spotted and nonspotted GLH from Bangladesh and the Philippines were similar, but those from Bangladesh had wider terminal abdominal segments and parameres, and more aedeagal setae. GLH males from the Philippines had more setae on the subgenital plate and anal tube. Spotted Philippine males had significantly longer parameres than those from Bangladesh. Also, the subgenital plate of nonspotted GLH males from the Philippines was significantly longer.

Females. GLH females were taken from stock cultures at BRRI and IRRI and preserved in 70% ethanol. Like the males, they had two distinct color morphs: one with black-spotted corium on the tegmen and the other with uniformly green tegmen. The spotted morph occurred

2. Abdominal terminalia of *N. virescens* female. A = ventral, B = dorsal, C = lateral views.

more frequently in both populations, but had relatively lower morphometric values (Table 2) in most genital and abdominal characters (Fig. 2).

GLH populations from both countries were similar in most morphological dimensions, except for the 10th abdominal segment.

Differences were particularly distinct in chaetotaxy. There were significantly more spines on the left and right pygofer of

GLH females from Bangladesh than on those from the Philippines. Philippine GLH had significantly more setae on the anal segment and the third valvula of their ovipositor.

The genital and abdominal dimensions and chaetotaxy of the two populations were stable morphological characters adequate enough to differentiate allopatric GLH populations from Bangladesh and the Philippines. □

A single-hole paper punch for dislodgeable pesticide residue on plant leaves

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The traditional dislodgeable residue sampler used in most of the Western laboratories is not available in India. We sought to develop a simple, economical, dislodgeable residue sampler (see figure).

We attached a stainless steel cup-and-hold block to the main assembly of a

A simplified dislodgeable residue sampler.

single-hole paper punch. The diameter of the punch can be varied by using dif-

ferent sized cup and hole blocks. The punch costs about US\$10. □